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Next generation sequencing of oral keratinocytes with HPV E6/E7 oncogene expression.

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We demonstrate here by RNA-sequencing of oral keratinocytes following forced expression of the E6/E7 papillomavirus oncogenes silencing of multiple genes of the Kallikrein enzyme family including *Klk5*, *Klk7* and *Klk10*.

Citations

1. Park, N.H., Min, B.M., Li, S.L., Huang, M.Z. and Doniger, J., 1991. Immortalization of normal human oral keratinocytes with type 16 human papillomavirus. *Carcinogenesis*, 12(9), pp.1627-1631.

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